

Supporting Information

High Bandgap Perovskites for Efficient Indoor Light Harvesting

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1. Materials

Lead chloride (PbCl_2 , >99.999%), Toluene (99.8%), N,N'-dimethylformamide (DMF) and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Lead acetate ($\text{Pb}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$, >98.0%), C₆₀-fused N-Methylpyrrolidine-*m*-C₁₂-phenyl (CMC) and bathocuproine (BCP, 99.0%), were purchased from TCI. Methylammonium iodide (MAI) and Methylammonium bromide (MABr) were purchased from Greatcell Solar. [6,6]-phenyl-C61-butyric acid methyl ester (PCBM) and indene-C60 bisadduct (ICBA) were purchased from Solenne (Netherlands). Poly[bis-(4-phenyl)-(2,4,6-trimethylphenyl)-amine] (PTAA, Mn = 17900, Mw = 33000) was purchased from Xi'an Polymer Light Technology Corp (China).

2. Device fabrication

2.1 Sample ITO/PTAA/CH₃NH₃PbI₃/PCBM/BCP/Ag

Devices and films were fabricated as discussed in ref. ^[1]. For the benefit of the reader, we provide a quote of this section below:

“The pre-patterned ITO substrates ($2.0 \times 2.0 \text{ cm}^2$) were bought from KINTEC and ultrasonically cleaned with soap (Hellmanex III), deionized water, acetone and IPA in succession for 10 min. The as-cleaned ITO substrates were treated with oxygen plasma (Diener Zepto, 50 W) for 12 min and transferred to a N₂-filled glovebox. 80 μl 75 °C PTAA (2.0 mg ml⁻¹ in toluene) solution was spin-coated onto the ITO substrates with a two-consecutive step program at 500 rpm for 4 s (with a ramping rate of 500 rpm s⁻¹) and 4500 rpm for 20 s (with a ramping rate of 800 rpm s⁻¹), then the samples were thermally annealed at 100 °C for 10 min and afterwards cooled down to room temperature. The perovskite precursor solution prepared by mixing $\text{Pb}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ (0.54 M), PbCl_2 (0.06 M), DMSO (0.6 M) and MAI (1.791 M) in DMF was stirred at room temperature for 24 h and filtered with a 0.45 μm PTFE filter prior to use. To fabricate the perovskite layer, 120 μl perovskite precursor solution was spin-coated on the top of

PTAA layer by a two-consecutive step program at 1600 rpm for 15 s (with a ramping rate of 350 rpm s^{-1}) and 6000 rpm for 40 s with a ramping rate of 767 rpm s^{-1} . The samples were immediately annealed on a hotplate at $75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 min. Afterwards they were cooled down to room temperature and a PCBM blend solution ($60 \text{ }\mu\text{l}$, preheated to $75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 20 mg ml^{-1} in CB) was spin-coated on the top of perovskite layer at a speed of 1200 rpm for 60 s (with a ramping rate of 400 rpm s^{-1}). Finally, BCP (8 nm) and Ag (80 nm) were thermally evaporated sequentially in a separate vacuum chamber ($<5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ Pa}$)."

2.2 Sample

ITO/PTAA/ $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{Pb}(\text{I}_{0.8}\text{Br}_{0.2})_3$ /PCBM/BCP/Ag

ITO/PTAA/ $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{Pb}(\text{I}_{0.8}\text{Br}_{0.2})_3$ /PCBM:CMC/BCP/Ag

ITO/PTAA/ $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{Pb}(\text{I}_{0.8}\text{Br}_{0.2})_3$ /CMC:ICBA/BCP/Ag

Devices and films were fabricated as discussed in ref. ^[2]. For the benefit of the reader, we provide a quote of this section below:

"The pre-patterned ITO substrates ($2.0 \times 2.0 \text{ cm}^2$) were bought from Advanced Election Technology Co., Ltd and ultrasonically cleaned with soap (Hellmanex III), deionized water, acetone and IPA in succession for 10 min. The as-cleaned ITO substrates were treated with oxygen plasma (Diener Zepto, 50 W) for 12 min and transferred to a N_2 -filled glovebox. $80 \text{ }\mu\text{l}$ $75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ PTAA (2.0 mg ml^{-1} in toluene) solution was spin-coated onto the ITO substrates with a two-consecutive step program at 500 rpm for 4 s (with a ramping rate of 500 rpm s^{-1}) and 4500 rpm for 20 s (with a ramping rate of 800 rpm s^{-1}), then the samples were thermally annealed at $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 10 min and afterwards cooled down to room temperature. The perovskite precursor solution prepared by mixing $\text{Pb}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ (0.6 M), MAI (1.485 M) and MABr (0.36 M) in DMF was stirred at room temperature for 24 h and filtered with a $0.45 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ PTFE filter prior to use. To fabricate the perovskite layer, $120 \text{ }\mu\text{l}$ perovskite precursor solution was spin-coated on the top of PTAA layer by a two-consecutive step program at 1400 rpm for 15 s (with a ramping rate of 350 rpm s^{-1}) and 6000 rpm for 30 s with a ramping rate of 767 rpm s^{-1} . The samples were immediately annealed on a hotplate at $75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 min. Afterwards they were cooled down to room temperature and a PCBM or PCBM:CMC or CMC:ICBA (1:1: by weight) blend solution ($60 \text{ }\mu\text{l}$, preheated to $75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 10 mg ml^{-1} in CB) was spin-coated on the top of perovskite layer at a speed of 1200 rpm for 60 s (with a ramping rate of 400 rpm s^{-1}). Finally, BCP (8 nm) and Ag (80 nm) were thermally evaporated sequentially in a separate vacuum chamber ($<5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ Pa}$)."

3. LED light characterization

In this work the white LED lamp was used with OD1 neutral density filter. The power output of the LED lamp was controlled by the LED lamp current. LED spectra without the filter were measured with a compact array spectrometer from “Instrument Systems” at a predefined set of currents. The resulting normalized spectra are presented in **Figure S1(a)**. From these measurements, the dependence of power density on the LED current was determined by integrating the spectra (**Table S1**).

Figure S1 Normalized spectral irradiances of white LED lamp used in this study for different LED currents (0.84, 1.25, 1.85, 2.75, 4.07, 6.03, 8.95, 13.27, 18.7, 29.19, 43.26, 64.26, 95.34, 141.54, 210, 420, 630 mA) and normalized spectral irradiance of white LED lamp with OD1 filter (red line) for 210mA LED current (a). Dependence of power density of LED lamp with OD1 filter on LED current (b). The points marked with red were obtained by interpolation.

The spectral response of the neutral-density filter was calculated separately by measuring the spectrum of the LED lamp with the OD1 filter at 200 mA current. As the spectrum of the LED did not change with current, the power attenuation was determined from one measurement at 200 mA. The LED power densities with the filter were calculated by multiplying power densities without filter by the power attenuation coefficient of 0.10237. Finally, additional points were obtained by interpolation (Figure S1(b)).

Table S1 LED lamp power dependence on LED current (with and without OD1 filter). The points that were obtained by interpolation are marked with red color.

LED current [mA]	Measured LED power density no filter $[\text{W/m}^2]$	LED power density with OD1 filter $[\text{W/m}^2]$
0.84	0.2	0.02047

1		0.04543
1.25	0.87	0.08906
1.55		0.14776
1.85	2.07	0.21191
2.3		0.31524
2.75	4.14	0.42382
3.4		0.58405
4.07	7.32	0.74937
6.03	11.99	1.22745
8.95	19.31	1.97682
13.27	30.08	3.07937
18.7	46.7	4.78081
29.19	71.24	7.29303
43.26	107.84	11.03987
64.26	162.32	16.61714
95.34	242.44	24.81924
141.54	360.42	36.89717
210	531.53	54.41417
420	1034.45	105.89946
630	1510.38	154.6217

3.1 Illuminance calculation

To calculate illuminance of the LED light the measured spectral irradiance is multiplied by the photopic luminous efficiency function and integrated with respect to wavelength:

$$Ev = k \int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} V(\lambda)E(\lambda)d\lambda, \quad (1)$$

where Ev is the illuminance, k is a conversion constant ($k=683 \text{ lx(Wm}^{-2}\text{)}^{-1}$), V is the photopic luminous efficiency, and E is the measured spectral irradiance of LED lamp. This was done for the measured LED spectrum with OD1 filter and 210 mA LED current. As the spectrum of LED light does not depend on the current (Figure S1(a)), illuminance values for other LED currents were calculated proportionally to the power density obtained previously:

$$Ev(x) = Ev(210mA) * Pd(x) / Pd(210), \quad (2)$$

Where Ev is illuminance of the LED lamp and Pd is power density. Resulting values of illuminance are presented in **Table S2**.

Table S2 Illuminance dependence on LED current for white LED with OD1 filter

LED current [mA]	LED power density with OD1 filter [W/m ²]	Illuminance proportional to power [lx]
0.84	0.02047	4.777
1	0.04543	10.600
1.25	0.08906	20.779
1.55	0.14776	34.475
1.85	0.21191	49.441
2.3	0.31524	73.548
2.75	0.42382	98.882
3.4	0.58405	136.263
4.07	0.74937	174.834
6.03	1.22745	286.375
8.95	1.97682	461.209
13.27	3.07937	718.444
18.7	4.78081	1115.404
29.19	7.29303	1701.528
43.26	11.03987	2575.699
64.26	16.61714	3876.923
95.34	24.81924	5790.54513
141.54	36.89717	8608.432
210	54.41417	12695.300
420	105.89946	24707.265
630	154.6217	36074.58981

To validate this method of calculation of illuminance we perform the same calculation for a set of spectra measured at different currents without OD1 filter (Figure S1(a)). The resulting values are presented in (Table S3 column 3) together with the values obtained directly from the spectrum integration for each point` (Table S3 column 4). Values for 210 mA match exactly as this value was used as initial one for proportionality formula. All values of illuminance are equal to values obtained by direct integration within 1% tolerance except for the lowest values of 51.487 and 223.967, which deviate by 2.9% and 3.5% respectively.

Table S3 Comparison of the illuminance values obtained by spectrum integration and the values proportional to LED power density.

LED current [mA]	Power density [W/m ²]	Illuminance proportional to power [lx]	Illuminance from spectra [lx]
0.84	0.2	51.487	49.989
1.25	0.87	223.967	216.085

1.85	2.07	532.886	530.946
2.75	4.14	1065.772	1063.468
4.07	7.32	1884.409	1867.129
6.03	11.99	3086.620	3070.791
8.95	19.31	4971.029	4939.416
13.27	30.08	7743.581	7707.131
18.7	46.7	12022.116	11974.733
29.19	71.24	18339.519	18270.645
43.26	107.84	27761.563	27642.525
64.26	162.32	41786.507	41676.304
95.34	242.44	62412.030	62321.815
141.54	360.42	92783.962	92682.005
210	531.53	136833.304	136833.304
420	1034.45	266301.452	267366.597
630	1510.38	388821.487	391093.775

References

- [1] Z. Liu, L. Krückemeier, B. Krogmeier, B. Klingebiel, J. A. Márquez, S. Levchenko, S. Öz, S. Mathur, U. Rau, T. Unold, T. Kirchartz, ACS Energy Letters 2019, 4, 110.
- [2] Z. Liu, J. Siekmann, B. Klingebiel, U. Rau, T. Kirchartz, Advanced Energy Materials 2021, 11, 2003386.